

youth
SKILLS

**Report on the effects of ICT use on
attention-related cognitive functions
measured with ESM and fMRI**

**Focus on ESM and fMRI methods to
measure effects of ICT skills and use on
wellbeing and cognitive functions**

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Report on the effects of ICT use on attention-related cognitive functions measured with ESM and fMRI

Focus on ESM and fMRI methods to measure effects of ICT skills and use on wellbeing and cognitive functions

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Executive summary

This report presents methodologies that are developed and implemented in two studies investigating how information and communications technology (ICT) skills and use are associated with (1) adolescents' wellbeing on momentary and daily levels, as measured with experience sampling method (ESM), and (2) cognitive skills and related brain activity, as measured with cognitive tasks and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). Both studies are conducted in two countries: Finland and Belgium.

In the ESM study, two waves of intensive longitudinal data are collected from both countries, first in the start of the academic year and second two months later. The participants are 13- to 17-year-old adolescents who respond to six daily surveys with a momentary assessment app on their phones during a 14-day period in each wave. The questionnaires are designed to capture adolescents' daily ICT use (e.g., momentary ICT use and daily screen time) and aspects of their wellbeing, including emotions, self-efficacy, problematic social media use and sleep. Using ecologically valid momentary ESM assessments reduces recall bias and allows examining within-person effects and temporal processes underlying the links between ICT use and wellbeing.

In the fMRI study, the participants are 12- to 14-year-olds. They perform mathematical tasks during scanning of their brain activity with fMRI. In half of the conditions, their performance is distracted with task-irrelevant speech and babble mimicking classroom voices. The aim of this fMRI study is to determine whether ICT skills and use, measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire (see Appendix 1), are associated with performance and brain activity in these attention-demanding conditions. A preceding fMRI data collection in young adult participants has already indicated that the applied experimental settings are able to reveal modulations of brain activity related to mathematical task performance, control of attention, and distraction of task performance by task-irrelevant speech. The fMRI and behavioural results from 12- to 14-year-olds will be also compared with those obtained during semantic processing of written sentences at the presence or absence of distracting speech, and during semantic processing of spoken sentences at the presence or absence of distracting written text. Previous studies in adults and adolescents have shown that also these experimental settings efficiently reveal task-, attention-, and distraction-related changes in brain activity.

1 Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 15 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12- to 17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

ySKILLS will **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing will be critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

This report contributes to achieving the second objective of ySKILLS by focusing on how ICT use and skills impact children's wellbeing and cognitive functions. More specifically, this report presents the development of methods for measuring these effects with experience sampling method (ESM) and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI).

ySKILLS has proposed, and will continue to develop, its **conceptual model** (see Figure 1):

1.2 This report

This report presents the methods from Tasks 4.4 and 4.5 that aim to elucidate impacts of ICT skills and use on adolescents' wellbeing and cognitive and brain function in attention-demanding tasks. To this end, ESM and fMRI data collections were conducted in two countries: Belgium and Finland. In this report, we present the methods of data collection of these studies examining the short-term impacts of ICT use and skills on cognitive and psychological wellbeing.

This report describes the conceptual definitions of the phenomena examined in this study, that is adolescents' ICT use, wellbeing, and cognitive skills and related brain activity. We also describe the rationale for using the methods developed to study these phenomena. Moreover, the development and implementation of this methodology in the two studies is described.

2 Background

2.1 Measuring the effects of ICT use on wellbeing with ESM

Most of the academic literature on adolescents' digital engagement and its correlates is based on cross-sectional self-report studies (see e.g., Science Advice Initiative of Finland, 2021; Hietajärvi et al., 2022a), which, while informative in many ways, due to their cross-sectional nature are unable to provide insight on either the short-term effects of digital media use or the long-term developmental dynamics. To move further, approaches allowing for the estimation of within-person (i.e., intraindividual) effects have been championed (see e.g., Hamaker, 2012). Moving from between-person (i.e., interindividual) analyses towards more nuanced within-person analyses gives us novel pathways towards examining the effects of digital engagement *in situ*, as well as directionality of effects and thus provides pathways towards eventually understanding possible causal effects. To do so, multiple repeated measurements are needed from the same participant and the experience sampling method (ESM; see Hektner et al., 2017) is one of the most practical yet ecologically valid approaches to gather such data.

ESM (also referred to as ecological momentary assessment) is a method for collecting momentary survey data, typically via mobile devices. It allows researchers to collect intensive longitudinal data on individuals' daily lives. In other words, researchers are able to capture situations or moments repeatedly and almost in real time. There are several benefits for this kind of data (Salmela-Aro et al., 2017). First, ESM is well suited for assessing situational or context-specific behaviour and experiences, such as ICT use and affective states. Second, as the assessment is on a momentary basis, it is less susceptible to retrospective bias, in other words error due to the inaccuracy in reporting experiences recalled from the past (Bolger et al., 2003; Robinson & Clore, 2002). Third, data collection takes part in real world settings, increasing its ecological validity. Fourth, it allows for easy ways of collecting repeated measures from the same participants leading to higher reliability. Finally, as noted earlier, intensive longitudinal data allow the disentangling of within-person processes from between-person differences and contextual effects and to examine the temporal relationships within these processes.

2.1.1 ICT use beyond screen time

As noted earlier, the academic literature on digital media use has been limited by relying mainly on cross-sectional self-report data. However, this is not the only limitation. In terms of measurement, digital media use has often been operationalized as self-reported screen time, aiming to capture all time spent using any digital device and doing anything at all. Such approach is conceptually very limited (Hietajärvi et al., 2019, Science Advice Initiative of Finland, 2021), to say the least, and biased if relying on self-reported data (Parry et al., 2021). While using the ESM we are still relying on self-report data, its validity increases through assessing the activity *in situ*, thus minimizing retrospective bias. Further, it is imperative to capture the qualitative differences and move “beyond screen time” and study the variation across different conditions or situations, as the dynamic effects of digital engagement are hypothesised to differ as a function of the type of digital engagement (Hietajärvi et al., 2022b) as well as developmentally and contextually (Hietajärvi et al., 2022a, Valkenburg & Peter, 2013). In addition, ESM and a longitudinal approach enable examining the direction of effects and enhance different perspectives on ICT use, such as *the technology selection perspective* (meaning that mental health is assumed to be the causal factor explaining amount or types of ICT usage) or *the technology effects perspective* (meaning that ICT use is the causal factor contributing to adolescents' mental health; Meier et al., 2020).

2.1.2 ICT use and wellbeing

A key objective in ySKILLS is to examine the effects of adolescents' ICT use on their cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing. In this study, momentary and daily measures are used to examine several short-term outcomes, such as problematic social media use, basic psychological needs, emotions, and sleep.

Empirical evidence of problematic social media use indicates that it is a growing mental health problem among adolescents (Boer et al., 2020). The use of social media may turn into being problematic depending on the interplay between individual characteristics, proximal and distal contexts and the feature of the digital application(s) adolescents are engaged with. However, there is a lack of scientific evidence that explains how problematic social media use occurs in adolescents' lives and what kind of impact it has on the daily level processes. ESM gives opportunities to study the different daily dynamics related to (problematic) social media use and adolescent wellbeing. ESM also helps researchers to understand the different mechanisms that lie beneath the overall concept of time spent in social media. In addition, it can brighten our understanding of the individual characteristics and contextual factors that provide individuals with some form of coping resources to resist the negative influences of social media.

Self-determination theory (SDT) posits that human motivation for an activity can be either *autonomous* (i.e., from within an individual) or *controlled* (i.e., externally imposed or controlled), or the motivation and intention might be lacking (i.e., *amotivation*). Moreover, the type of activity, rather than just the amount, predicts performance as well as social and psychological health outcomes (Ryan, 2009; Deci & Ryan, 1980; Ryan & Deci, 2017). The type and strength of motivation depends on the degrees to which universal basic psychological needs for *autonomy*, *competence*, and *relatedness* are supported or thwarted. Most importantly, when these needs are satisfied, people experience vitality, self-motivation, and wellbeing (Ryan 2009; Deci & Ryan, 1980; Ryan & Deci, 2017). Although today there exists an enormous amount of literature on self-determination, there is hardly any research on the links between self-determination and ICT use, yet alone on a daily basis (Rigby & Ryan, 2016).

The effects of ICT use on young people's wellbeing have been a significant driver of research. However, little research has been conducted on the effects on ICT use on young people's affective wellbeing, in other words adolescents' emotions that reflect affective evaluations of their life events (Eid & Diener, 2004). Emotions can be characterized based on two dimensions, valence (positive–negative or pleasure–displeasure) and arousal (activation–deactivation; e.g., Barrett et al., 2007; Pekrun, 2006; Russell, 1980). For example, enthusiasm is a positive activating emotion whereas boredom is a negative disactivating emotion. Affective experiences vary in length. Emotions are relatively short-lived and intense and can be distinguished from more stable affect dispositions (e.g., Scherer, 2005). The integrative model of ICT effects on adolescents' wellbeing (Smahel et al., 2022) suggests that short- and long-term effects between the two can differ or even be opposite. It is possible that ICT use is more likely to influence momentary state emotions instead of more robust long-term wellbeing. Moreover, as emotions are short-lived (Verduyn et al., 2009) and susceptible to retrospective bias (Robinson & Clore, 2002), they are difficult to capture with traditional survey methods. ESM allows assessing the affective outcomes of ICT use in situ, thus reducing this bias.

Already in 2013, Gradisar and colleagues (2013) reported that the majority of people (from adolescence to adulthood) used some form of digital media within the hour before going to bed. Digital engagement has been associated with later bedtimes and problems falling asleep (Lund et al., 2021), but the evidence relays mainly on cross-sectional data and does not reveal the causal relationships. In addition, cross-sectional datasets do not capture the timing of usage or the daily level

dynamics between digital technology use and how it might interfere with sleep. Academic literature has started to move forward by focusing on the different forms of digital engagement and psychosocial measures in place of capturing only overall time spent on screens. By measuring different types of usage (etc. chatting with friends or reading the news) and related psychosocial or attitudinal measures, it is possible to capture their different effects (Steele et al., 2020) and bring out individual differences that explain why some individuals are more susceptible to have sleep difficulties due to digital technology than others are. In addition, the timing of usage is important when examining the effects ICT use may have on adolescent sleep and with the help of ESM it is easier to capture ICT use close to bedtime (Maksniemi et al., 2022). Moreover, ESM allows measuring sleep duration and subjective sleep quality early in the morning, which reduces retrospective bias and leads to accurate assessments.

In sum, adolescents' daily ICT use is likely to have short-term effects on different aspects of their wellbeing. Social media use may have problematic and harmful outcomes. However, digital engagement may also facilitate feelings of autonomy, competence and relatedness. Digital engagement is also associated with short-term affective wellbeing (i.e., emotions; Eid & Diener, 2004). Moreover, ICT use may affect adolescents' sleep and sleeping behaviour, which, in turn, has an impact on daily functioning (Maksniemi et al., 2022). These short-term effects may differ from those that are observable on longer time scales or using dispositional or trait-level measures. ESM allows collecting momentary assessments of these short-term effects improving ecological validity and minimising retrospective bias. Moreover, it allows moving beyond examining between-person differences and rather investigating the temporal and within-person processes associated with these phenomena (Salmela-Aro et al., 2017).

2.2 Effects of ICT use on cognitive skills and related brain activity (fMRI)

According to previous studies applying measurements of performance and brain activity during experimental tasks, the ways people use digital technology may affect their cognitive functions. For instance, research in adolescents and young adults has suggested that while frequent video gaming may enhance attention skills, frequent multitasking in daily life may deteriorate these skills and enhance distractibility (for a review, see Alho, Moisala & Salmela-Aro, 2022). In one of such studies, Moisala et al. (2017) recorded brain activity of healthy Finnish adolescents and young adults with fMRI during a working-memory task that also demanded switching of attention between auditorily and visually delivered to-be-memorised items (spoken and written vowels). In this study with 167 participants (a large number for a cognitive fMRI experiment), those participants who played video games more frequently were faster and more accurate in their task performance and showed higher prefrontal brain activity, this activity presumably being associated with control of attention and maintenance of items in working memory.

In another fMRI experiment, Moisala et al. (2016) studied an overlapping group of 149 adolescents and young adults and found frequent daily multitasking (e.g., texting during video watching or listening to music during reading) to be associated with higher distractibility and related right brain activity. Distractibility was indicated by reduced number of correct responses during an experimental task where written sentences were to be classified as semantically congruent (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of cereal") or incongruent (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of shoes") at the presence of unrelated spoken sentences or music (compared with a similar condition without speech or music distractors), and during a task where spoken sentences were to be classified as congruent or incongruent at the presence of unrelated written distractor sentences (compared with no text on the screen).

The findings described above, and related results from other studies, lead us to design an fMRI paradigm applied in the ySKILLS project, where participants solve closed or open mathematical problems in conditions distracted and not distracted by task-irrelevant speech, mimicking voices in a classroom. We also reasoned that mathematical tasks are highly suitable for simulating academic performance at school, since cognitive processes during mathematical problem solving may be assumed to be highly similar irrespective of the environment, whether, for instance, a classroom or an MRI laboratory.

2.3 Aims of the current research

2.3.1 Aims of the ESM study

The aim of the ESM study is to understand the short-term associations of adolescents' ICT skills and use with their wellbeing, more specifically momentary emotions, daily problematic social media use and self-efficacy in ICT use, and sleep. To this end, we collected intensive longitudinal data from 400 adolescents in total (aged 13 to 17) from Belgium and Finland, to allow cross-country comparison. The data were collected during the adolescents' daily lives in two 14-day waves in both countries. This kind of data allow the examination of within-person dynamics, contexts and processes in which daily and momentary digital engagement and wellbeing are associated. The research design builds on our team's previous work on developing methods to collect and analyse intensive longitudinal data on adolescents' daily and momentary engagement and wellbeing in different contexts (J. Inkinen et al., 2020; M. Inkinen et al., 2014; Järvinen et al., 2022; Ketonen et al., 2022).

2.3.2 Aims of the fMRI study

In the fMRI studies conducted in Finland, the goal is to collect fMRI and performance data from 80 Finnish 12- to 13-year-olds during mathematical problem solving at the presence or absence of distracting speech and to study associations of participants' performance and brain activity in different conditions with their digital skills and digital technology according to their answers to the ySKILLS questionnaire. Related to this, a previous study by Pagani et al. (2016) including over 1400 Italian high-school students found that the students with better self-reported digital skills received higher scores in national tests in mathematics. The mathematical problem-solving paradigm used in these fMRI studies of the ySKILLS project was also used in an ongoing six-year research project titled '*Growing Mind: Educational transformations for facilitating sustainable personal, social, and institutional renewal at the digital age*' and funded by the Finnish Strategic Research Council. Altogether 105 healthy 12- to 14-year-old Finnish participants in this fMRI experiment, conducted in 2021–2022, in the Growing Mind project also completed the ySKILLS questionnaire. We will combine their fMRI and performance data with the data from the 80 ySKILLS participants. Moreover, 61 Growing Mind participants also participated in an fMRI experiment including the conditions used also in the study of Moisala et al. (2016; see above) where written sentences were to be classified as congruent/incongruent at the presence or absence of distracting spoken sentences and spoken sentences were to be classified as congruent or incongruent at the presence or absence of distracting written sentences. This allows us to compare associations of digital skills with distractibility during semantic and mathematical tasks, despite all differences between the applied tasks and the distractors delivered during them.

Attention and working memory are critical determinants of performance in mathematical tasks (e.g., Bellon et al., 2019; De Smedt, 2022; Spiegel et al., 2021). To clarify their contributions to associations of digital skills and mathematical performance possibly found in the fMRI study, we conducted in Belgium an additional behavioural study determining associations between ICT skills and attention and working memory. The participants' ICT skills were measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire

and ICT performance test. Their attention and working memory skills, in turn, were measured with classic tasks widely used in experimental studies, namely the Flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974) and the n-back task (e.g., Pelegrina et al., 2015), respectively. For a detailed description of these experimental tasks, see the section 3.3.2.1.

3 Methodology

3.1 ESM study

3.1.1 Data and sample

To assess the short-term impact of adolescents' ICT skills and use on their wellbeing, two ESM data collections were conducted in both Belgium and Finland during the autumn of 2022. The data collections were conducted simultaneously in both countries in close collaboration with schools. The first ESM wave was collected in August and September 2022 and second wave in November 2022. In addition, all participants completed (or will complete) a survey assessing their digital skills (yDSI) and background information, among others. The participants in the Finnish sample participated in the longitudinal survey study in spring 2022 and/or will participate in the next collection in spring 2023. Since Belgium is not one of the ySKILLS survey countries, participants were recruited from secondary schools that did not participate in earlier ySKILLS research. Therefore, all adolescents filled in a survey with background information and the yDSI questionnaire at the beginning of the data collection.

At the moment of writing this report in December 2022 the data collection for the second wave is still ongoing. Table 1 shows the descriptive overview of the sample of the first wave of the ESM data collection. The participants were 439 students from seven different secondary schools. The Belgian sample consisted of third to sixth grade secondary school students (13 to 17 years old) from four schools, whereas the Finnish sample consisted of first year upper secondary school students (15 to 16 years old) from three schools.

Table 1.	First ESM wave sample description by country	
	Belgium	Finland
Number of adolescents	294	145
Age	13–17	15–16
% girls	64	66
Number of schools	4	3
Number of responses	7,075	2,503

3.1.2 Procedure

The study is conducted simultaneously in Finland and Belgium during the autumn 2022. The planned onset of the data collection in spring 2022 was delayed due to COVID-19-related challenges and difficulties in recruiting schools and participants for the study. The planning of the data collection was done in collaboration among the researchers of University of Helsinki, University of Turku and KU Leuven as well as with the schools taking part in the study.

One of the first challenges was to find the platform for ESM data collection. Different options (e.g., nEMA, AWARE Framework and m-Path) were considered and compared in terms of technical specifications, data handling, survey options, and workflow among others. After hands-on testing, m-Path was selected due to pricing, clarity of the dashboard, workflow, technical aspects and data handling (the data were stored only in EU servers). Another important aspect was the availability of technical support, which is conveniently located in KU Leuven where the software was developed.

m-Path (Mestdagh et al., 2022) is a GDPR compliant platform for momentary questionnaires developed at the KU Leuven. The platform was originally developed for psychiatric practitioners, but it has been used to run ESM studies as it has all necessary features for this purpose. The platform does not collect any personal data, and the connection between researchers and participants relies on a user-given aliases and device-server encrypted identities. There is no need to handle any personal information in the process. Thus, it is not possible to directly connect the data located on servers to any of the participants.

In m-Path, questionnaires and timetables are set up for participants in the dashboard. Participants can use their own phone or a research phone connected to the internet. We considered the advantages and disadvantages of either giving the participants research phones or having them download the application to their own phones. We settled for the latter due to practical reasons, as it would be cumbersome for the participants to carry another phone. Moreover, a mobile internet connection would be required for all research phones.

All surveys are triggered from web servers and the user will see notifications on their phone. After the user responds to a survey, the data are stored in the servers and on the user's phone. The user can delete their data from the phone and servers or end their participation in the study at any time. The platform provides possibility for restoring an account using a personal restoration code that a user can obtain from the app in case of, for example losing or breaking the phone.

The study was conducted in a similar way in Finland and Belgium. In both countries, participants attended to a class where they were informed about the study and consented to participating in the study (Appendix 5) before the start of the data collection. They were instructed on how to install the m-Path app in their phones, how to respond to the surveys, and how to check the screen time log data on their phone. However, due to the different educational systems and collaboration with different schools, there were notable differences in the procedures between the countries. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee in the Humanities and Social and Behavioural Sciences of University of Helsinki, Finland, and the Social and Societal Ethics Committee (SMEC) of KU Leuven, Belgium. The specific procedures in each country are described below.

3.1.2.1 Procedure in Finland

The initial objective in Finland was to collect the first wave of ESM data parallel to the longitudinal survey in March 2022. This was agreed upon with the city of Salo when the ySKILLS project was launched. However, due to unexpected COVID-related reorganisation of teaching, distance learning, and increased stress among teachers and students during 2021 and 2022, schools became reluctant to participate in research. In the beginning of 2022, we were informed that the ESM data collection had to be postponed to April or May due to work overload, and later that it had to be postponed to the fall. Regarding the sample, our initial objective was to retrieve a sample of 200 lower secondary school pupils (grades 8 and 9, ages 14 to 16) in order to follow the development of younger adolescents. However, in the beginning of 2022 it became evident that lower secondary schools were more reluctant to participate in the ESM than upper secondary schools. Hence, our focus was turned to the latter also due to the problems with receiving parental consent encountered in conjunction with

the longitudinal survey. That is, active parental consent is not required with upper secondary school students, who are 15 years of age or older.

Three upper secondary schools (all upper secondary schools in the city of Salo) participated in the ESM study. The schools informed the participants and their parents about the study by sending the consent information via email about one week before the study. In the beginning of both ESM data collection waves, the tenth-grade students (first year in upper secondary school) at each school (n = 287) participated in a 30-minute session where they were instructed on the study procedures. In addition to a PowerPoint presentation including information and instructions shown in the session, the participants were given instructions about the study on paper, and those who were absent were given instructions afterwards so they could join the study even if they were absent from the session. Before the data collection, the purpose of the study was explained to all the participants. They were informed about how the ESM data was collected, stored and handled. It was explained that participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study or cancel their consent at any point without consequences. Before the study, the participants filled in an informed consent form (Appendix 5). Their parents were given the same consent information and had the option to actively decline the participation of their child, but parental consent was not required as the participants were above the age of 15.

The participants were instructed how to install m-Path application and how to respond to the ESM questionnaires. The participants were given an identification code to log in to m-Path and instructed not to share any personal information in the app. This way the responses of an individual could be linked to their longitudinal survey information securely without storing personal information with the data.

3.1.2.2 Procedure in Belgium

To recruit adolescents willing to participate in the study, we started in March 2022. Via Mediawijs, the Flemish Knowledge Centre for Digital and Media Literacy, we got the opportunity to contact adolescents that participated in an earlier study on media use. All adolescents who gave consent to be contacted again in the future were sent an email. This email included information on the ySKILLS ESM study that would take place in May and November 2022, together with two online consent forms: one for themselves, and one for their parents (in case they were below 16 years old). In total, we contacted about 200 adolescents. However, only three of them completed the consent form.

In April 2022, as a second attempt to recruit participants, schools were contacted with information about the research and an invitation to participate in the study in May and November 2022. Since the end of the school year – and thus the exam period - was approaching, the schools were reluctant to participate.

In May 2022, we decided to postpone the first wave of data collection to September 2022. A flyer with information on the study (see Figure 2) was shared in a Facebook group with Flemish secondary school teachers. We also offered a school session on digital skills as a compensation for participating in the study. In total, near 98 teachers requested more information on the ESM study. Every teacher was sent an email with information and practical details on the ESM study, together with an invite to schedule an online meeting. In the end, teachers of four schools, with in total about 300 pupils, agreed to participate.

In late August, we scheduled a second online meeting with every teacher to discuss the practicalities of the data collection. We shared the consent forms for the adolescents and parents, together with a PowerPoint presentation with instructions on how to install the app m-Path and what to expect. In the classes with adolescents below 16 years old, the teachers shared a parental consent form two weeks before the start of the study (see Appendix 5).

A few days before the start of the study, the teachers spent one class hour per class group on the introduction of the ESM study. During this session, the teacher showed the PowerPoint presentation with the instructions, so the pupils could install the app on their smartphone during the course. The pupils were also asked to read the study information in the app and to give consent if they agree to participate. After consent was given, the pupils received a questionnaire with basic questions on demographics and digital skills (yDSI). The daily ESM questions started a few days later, when all pupils were well prepared.

For the second wave in November, all teachers received instructions two weeks before the start of the data collection. A message with instructions directed to the pupils was shared, so that the teachers could share this message on their online learning platform to inform the pupils about the start of the second wave and what to do in case of any problems. The second wave of the ESM study started a few days after the autumn break.

3.1.2.2 The ESM data collection

During the two-week study period, the participants were prompted with six ESM questionnaires per day. Two of the questionnaires were diary-type questionnaires: The morning questionnaire (Appendix 3), tapping into aspects of sleep and ICT use before and after sleeping, and the evening questionnaire (Appendix 4), asking the participants about their ICT use during the day. The morning questionnaire was sent to the participants at 7 am and they had until 12 pm (3 pm during weekends) to respond to it. The evening questionnaire was scheduled at 9.15 pm and the participants were instructed to respond before midnight. A momentary questionnaire (Appendix 2)—aimed to capture state emotions and ICT use in the moment—was programmed to occur four times a day with random intervals. Specifically, the signals were simultaneous for all participants and programmed to occur each within

four three-hour time periods between 9 am and 9 pm. The notification was programmed to time out after 30 minutes.

3.1.3 Measures

The momentary measures were designed to capture situational ICT use and state emotions, whereas the diary measures targeted daily ICT use and wellbeing. Some of the scales, such as the measures assessing state emotions, have been used in previous ESM studies (see J. Inkinen et al., 2020; Järvinen et al., 2022; Ketonen et al., 2022). Back-translation was not used but the consistency of the items in both languages were established by translating the scales into English and reviewed by a native researcher.

3.1.3.1 Momentary measures (momentary questionnaire)

In the beginning of the momentary questionnaire, the participants were prompted with a multiple-choice question: “What were you doing when you received the survey?” The response options were: “I was in class”; “I was in school, but not in class”; “I had free time/not in school”; and “Something else, what?”. If participant responded with the last option, they could further specify their response in an open-ended item.

ICT use in different situations was measured with several questions that were related to each other. First, participants reported whether they were using any digital device in the moment when they received the questionnaire. Response options were ‘Yes’ or ‘No’. If they chose ‘Yes’, they were asked to specify further what they were doing with the device. There were eight options to choose from and it was possible to choose multiple options: “I messaged/communicated with others”; “I browsed social media”; “I browsed websites (e.g., news, information)”; “I watched a series/movie/program (e.g., Netflix)”; “I played a game”; “I created photos/videos/blog texts myself”; “I listened to music”; and “something else, what?”. If respondents responded having browsed social media, they were further asked to select which social media platform they were browsing: TikTok, Instagram, Snapchat, YouTube, Facebook or “some other, what?”. If they chose the option “I browsed websites (e.g., news, information)”, they were asked to specify further which types of websites they were browsing: “politics (e.g., war)”; “economics”; “health (e.g., covid19)”; “entertainment, media, art and culture”; “sports”; “something else, what?”; “I don’t remember”. If they chose the option “I created photos/videos/blog texts myself”, they were further asked whether they shared their content and on which platform. The response options were the same as previously regarding social media browsing.

State emotions were measured with a short and modified version of PANAS (The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule; Watson et al., 1988). The scale was modified to be compact for the momentary assessment as well as to fit the context of adolescents’ daily lives, ICT use and wellbeing. The participants were prompted with a question: “How well do the following words describe your feelings now? At the moment I feel...” The list of emotion words included at least one emotion from each of the four following categories: positive activating (i.e., “enthusiastic”), positive deactivating (i.e., “relaxed”), negative activating (e.g., “anxious”) and negative deactivating (i.e., “bored”; see Appendix 2 for the full list of items). In addition, the feeling of loneliness was assessed. The participants rated each with a scale of 1 *not at all* to 7 *very much*.

3.1.4.2 Diary measures (morning and evening questionnaires)

News sharing and exposure to mis- and disinformation was measured with several questions in the evening questionnaire. First, participants were asked “Did you share a news item online today?”. If they responded ‘Yes’, they were asked whether they had read the news article, and what was the news

item about. Next, participants were asked whether they had seen a news item that made them doubt its credibility (“Have you seen a news item today that made you doubt whether it was real or fake?”). If they responded ‘Yes’, they were asked on which platform they had seen the message and what it was about.

Online comment reading was assessed by asking participants whether they had read online comments that day. If they responded ‘Yes’, they were asked what kind of comments they had read: ‘funny’, ‘offensive’, ‘informative’, ‘other’ or ‘I don’t remember/I don’t know’ and on which platform they had read the comment on. In case the participant had read an offensive comment, we asked to whom the comment was directed: “me personally”; “some other person”; “the group I belong to or identify with (e.g., gender, ethnicity)”; “a group someone else is part of/identifies with (e.g., gender, ethnicity)”; or “I don’t know/I’m not sure”.

Problematic social media use was measured with three items that were modified versions from the Social Media Disorder Scale (van den Eijnden et al., 2016). Problematic social media use during the day was measured each evening with one item assessing each of the three dimensions: *withdrawal* (“I felt bad when I could not use social media?”), *problems* (“I had arguments with others because of my social media use?”) and *deception* (“I lied to my parents or friends about the amount of time I spend on social media?”). The items were rated on a five-point scale (1 *Not at all*, 2 *A little*, 3 *To some degree*, 4 *Quite much*, 5 *A lot*).

Objective screen time was captured by asking the participants to report the log data from their personal smartphones each evening. They were instructed to check the log data and write the name of three most used applications and the hours and minutes they used each app. The participants were shown how to access the log data with different operating systems before the study.

Self-determination in ICT use: The links between daily ICT use and self-determination was measured in the ESM study each evening with four items tapping into the basic psychological needs. The participants were prompted with “Using digital devices today (e.g., mobile phone), I felt that I...” following the items: “...learned something new”, “...made a difference”, “...got to express myself”, and “...was part of a group/collective”. Items were rated on a scale ranging from 1 *not at all* to 5 *very much*.

Sleep and ICT use: Bedtime, sleep quality and related ICT use were measured with several questions. First, the participants were asked to reflect their ICT use 30 minutes before going to sleep with a multiple-choice question. The response options included, for example, “I read a book”, “I browsed social media” and “I watched a series/movie/program (e.g., Netflix)” (see Appendix 3 for all response options). If the participant reported browsing social media, they were asked to specify, which social media channel they were browsing. If they chose the option “I browsed websites (e.g., news, information)”, the participants were asked to report what kind of websites specifically. The response options included, for example, “health (e.g., covid19)”, “entertainment, media, art and culture” and “sports”. In addition, if the participant responded that “I created photos/videos/blog post texts myself”, they were asked to report if they shared their creation and, if yes, on which social media platform. Self-reported bedtime and wake-up time were measured with an open-ended question each, and the difference was calculated to acquire self-reported sleep duration. Phone use while in bed (“Did you use your phone in bed right before you started to sleep?”) and problems falling asleep (“Did you fall asleep easily?”) were measured with one dichotomous (‘Yes’ or ‘No’) item each. The participants were asked to assess how well they slept on a 5-point scale (1 *well*, 2 *quite well*, 3 *moderately*, 4 *quite badly*, 5 *badly*). Lastly, the participants were asked to report, whether they used their phone immediately as they woke up.

3.1.3 Data handling and statistical analysis

The data are saved in m-Path servers without the participants' personal information and downloaded for analysis in full format. The data consist of all responses as well as a row per each scheduled questionnaire that is not responded to. The data are read with R statistical programming language (R Core Team, 2022) and the rows with missing responses to the entire form are removed. The time variables (e.g., scheduled and response times) are coded to Eastern European Time (EET) time. The data are saved in one file, and, in addition, there are separate files for each questionnaire type. The data files are stored in SPSS file format. Multiple-choice variables (in string format) are coded into a new dummy variable per response choice. The data can be combined with ySKILLS longitudinal survey responses using pseudonyms created for each participant.

The ESM data are intensive longitudinal data with multiple responses per participant. Thus, they are organised in a hierarchical manner with moments (and diary responses) nested within individuals (participants). Accordingly, multilevel analytical approaches are used in analysing the data (see e.g., Muthén & Asparouhov, 2010). This controls for the systematic error caused by the nestedness in the data and allows partitioning the within- and between-person effects in the models, which in turn allows going beyond between-person differences in ICT use and wellbeing. Rather, it is possible to investigate the within-person processes of how ICT use and wellbeing are related (see Hamaker, 2012). For instance, we can examine whether increases or decreases in some form of digital engagement leads to changes in wellbeing. Moreover, the temporal dynamics and directionality of the effects between ICT use and wellbeing can be investigated further with dynamic modeling of the intensive longitudinal data (e.g., DSEM; Asparouhov et al., 2018).

3.2 fMRI study

3.2.1 Participants

The fMRI data collection in Finland in an estimated 80 12- to 13-year-olds will be completed in Spring 2023. However, the final sample will include an estimated 185 12- to 14-year-olds, 105 of them being participants in a similar experiment in 2021–2022 in the Growing Mind project funded by the Strategic Research Council of Finland. All participants are volunteers recruited from the schools of greater Helsinki area with an average or higher grade (7 or higher on a scale from 4 to 10) in school mathematics according to the last grading. All of them are native Finnish speakers with normal or corrected-to-normal vision and have no self-reported history of neurological or psychiatric disorders. The suitability for fMRI scanning (e.g., no metal attached to the body) is screened following the standard procedures of the imaging faculty, Advanced Magnetic Imaging (AMI) Centre at Aalto University, Espoo, Finland. The experiment is conducted only after written informed consent from the participant and their legal guardian, and in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital District of Helsinki and Uusimaa, Finland. Each participant filled the ySKILLS questionnaire on their ICT use and skills.

3.2.2 Experimental conditions

3.2.2.1 Mathematical tasks

The mathematical fMRI experiment includes three tasks (Figure 3). In the Solve task, the participants are to solve arithmetic calculations shown on one side of a computer screen projected onto a mirror mounted on the head coil of the MRI scanner. The equations include both simple calculations with only one arithmetic operation (e.g., '3 + 4' or '10 : 5'), and complex calculations with two arithmetic operations (e.g., '5 + 1 · 3'). A portion of the complex calculations also include parentheses (e.g., '9 : (5 - 2)'). To solve the equations, the participants are to pick up numbers (from 0 to 9) on the other side of the screen by clicking them with a computer cursor (e.g., for the calculation '5 + 1 · 3 =' they

were to choose first '1' and then '5'). All four basic arithmetic operations are used in the calculations. In the Create task, the participants are given a target answer and a set of numbers and operators from which they are to construct equations that result in the given answer. In the Select task, the participants are presented with numeric symbols and in some cases also parentheses, and their task is to select the corresponding symbols. There are either one, two, three, or five numbers (e.g., '2', '2 6', '4 1 9', and '3 6 8 1 2', respectively) or three numbers and parentheses (e.g., '8 7 9' and '8 (3 2)', respectively). While requiring no calculation, the Select task was designed to control for visuo-perceptual and motor activity during the Solve and Create tasks. The participants perform the tasks in a self-paced manner in 62-s blocks using a trackball to move a cursor and click on the symbols on the screen. They can erase their answer by clicking a 'delete' button and when they are finished with a task line, they click a 'next' button, and the next line appears. There is no possibility to return to previous lines to change answers.

Figure 3. Mathematical tasks during fMRI

Screen shots from different conditions of the fMRI experiments are shown here. In the Solve (in Finnish: 'Ratkaise') task (top), the participants solve calculations shown on one side (randomly left or right) of a computer screen and pick up numbers needed in their answer from the other side of the screen by clicking them with a cursor (+) controlled with a trackball. In the Create ('Keksi') task (middle), the participants are shown a target answer and a set of numbers and operators from which they are to construct equations that result in the given answer. In the Select ('Valitse') task (bottom), they are presented with numeric symbols and, in some cases, also parentheses, and their task is to pick up the corresponding symbols. The participants can erase their answer by clicking 'Delete' ('Poista') button. When they are finished with a line, they click 'Next' ('Seuraava') button, and the next line appears. For further details, see text.

Two types of task-irrelevant auditory stimulations are delivered during the mathematical tasks. These are either dialogues between a girl and a boy with classroom babble in the auditory background or noise-vocoded versions (cutoffs at 50, 247, 1216, and 6000 Hz) of the same dialogues and babble (cf. Davis & Johnsruide, 2003). The dialogue plus babble distractor was designed to mimic distracting voices that could be heard in a classroom, whereas its less distracting noise-vocoded equivalent was used to create a meaningless stream of noise with the same audio-spectral features as those in the dialogue plus babble. During half of the periods of each mathematical task type, a dialogue plus babble distractor, and during the other half, its noise-vocoded equivalent, is delivered binaurally via inserted earphones. The intensity of auditory stimulation at each ear drum is about 80 dB SPL.

The noise from the fMRI scanner (ca. 102 dB SPL at participant's head) is attenuated with viscoelastic mattresses around and under the participant's head inside the coil, and by the earplugs of the inserted earphones. Altogether 12 different dialogues (and 12 noise-vocoded counterparts) are used, with each dialogue being presented only once (except for its noise-vocoded counterpart). The dialogues concern emotionally neutral everyday topics, such as the weather and hobbies. Each dialogue consists of 12 lines with the speaker alternating. The dialogues were recorded in a soundproof studio with two speakers, a boy and girl (both aged 12). The lines of each dialogue were recorded one line at a time. The recorded lines were then combined to form entire dialogues, each dialogue lasting 62 s (average line length 4.34 s). Then, a recording of classroom babble was added to the dialogues. These background tracks consisted of classroom sounds such as children's babble, although with no understandable speech. The background tracks were taken from a recording of classroom sounds distributed under the Creative Commons license (<https://freesound.org/people/reinsamba/sounds/73178/>). Excerpts of 62 s were cut from the original recording so that no words could be recognised and no other salient acoustic events were present. Finally, the tracks were low-pass filtered using a cutoff of 5000 Hz and normalized to the same peak sound energy.

There are four runs in the experiment, each consisting of six 62-s task blocks, two for each task type, one delivered together with the dialogue plus babble distractor and the other together with its less distracting noise-vocoded equivalent. The order of the eight blocks within a run is randomized, and each block is preceded by a written instruction informing about the task and followed by written feedback: "It went well!" (in Finnish).

3.2.2.2 *Semantic tasks*

In the semantic tasks, performed in the Growing Mind project in 2021 by 61 participants who also filled the ySKILLS questionnaire on ICT skills and use, Finnish semantically congruent and incongruent sentences were used as stimuli during the fMRI measurements. The sentences were presented either auditorily (speech delivered binaurally via headphones) or visually (text on a screen projected onto a mirror mounted on the head coil). Semantically congruent sentences were simple phrases, dealing with everyday subjects (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of cereal"). Incongruent sentences were created by taking a subset of the congruent sentences and changing the last word of the sentence to a semantically incongruent but syntactically plausible word (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of shoes"). The spoken sentences were spoken by a native Finnish speaking female. During the reading task, the participants were to classify written sentences, and during the listening task, spoken sentences, as incongruent or congruent by pressing a button under their right index or middle finger, respectively.

In the distracted reading and listening condition, each to-be-classified sentence was accompanied by a concurrent unrelated sentence delivered in the other modality, whereas in undistracted reading and listening conditions, no sentences were presented in the other modality. After each sentence, there

was a 1-s response window, during which a question mark was presented in the middle of the screen. Feedback (i.e., the percentage of correct responses in the block) was presented after each task block. Before each block, an instruction for the following task type was presented.

There were three experimental runs, and in each run, there were four different task blocks, that is, distracted reading, undistracted reading, distracted listening and undistracted listening, delivered in a random order. The participants practiced all four conditions outside the MRI scanner before the experiment. The same sentences were never used in the practice trial and during the actual measurements. The written sentences were presented for 2.5 seconds. However, during the first 2 seconds or auditorily (speech delivered via headphones), the last word was replaced with as many letters 'x' letters as there were letters in the last word revealed for the final 0.5 seconds of the trial. The spoken sentences had a duration of about 2.5 seconds. In the trials where both written and spoken sentences were presented, each spoken sentence was timed so that its last word started 2 seconds after the beginning of the trial, that is, at the same time when the last word in the written sentence was revealed. The intensity of spoken sentences was about 80 dB SPL at the eardrum.

3.2.3 fMRI data acquisition and analysis

Magnetic resonance imaging is performed at the AMI Centre (Aalto Neuroimaging, Aalto University School of Science, Finland) using a 3 Tesla Magnetom Skyra whole body scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany) with a 30-channel head coil (modified from a 32-channel head coil to enlarge the visual field by removing the parts in front of the eyes). The imaged volumes consist of 56 oblique axial slices of T2*-weighted echo-planar images (SMS-EPI, TR: 1300 ms, voxel matrix 96×96 , in-plane resolution: 2.5 mm isotropic, TE: 41 ms, flip angle: 65° , multiband factor: 4). After the last functional run, a high-resolution anatomical image is acquired (MPRAGE; see, e.g., Ylinen et al., 2022b).

fMRIPrep standard pipeline 20.2.5 is used to preprocess the functional and structural MRI data. For each of run of fMRI data the following preprocessing is performed: Motion correction using *mcfliirt* (FSL 5.0.9); slice-time correction using *3dTshift* (AFNI 20160207); and normalization into standard space (MNI152NLin6Asym). Confounding time-series for framewise displacement (FD), DVARS and three region-wise global signals are calculated based on the preprocessed fMRI data (Power et al., 2014; Jenkinson et al., 2002). Additionally, a set of physiological regressors are extracted to allow for component-based noise correction (*aCompCor*, Behzadi et al., 2007).

FEAT (FMRI Expert Analysis Tool, version 6.00), part of FSL (FMRIB's Software Library, www.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl), was used to perform two separate first level general linear model (GLM) analyses of the fMRI data. The first GLM assesses block-level activations related to the different tasks and distractors. For the mathematical tasks, this model includes a separate regressor for each combination of task and auditory stimulation type (speech+babble or noise), and for the semantic tasks, a regressor for each combination of task (reading or listening) and presence/absence of distractor sentences in the other modality. Both for the mathematical and semantic tasks there are also regressors for instructions and feedbacks. To account for motion, drift, and other nuisance factors, the following regressors are calculated by *fMRIPrep* in both GLMs: global signal, five *aCompCor* regressors explaining most of the variance, framewise displacement (FD), the six basic motion parameters along with their second powers and derivatives, and the discrete cosine basis functions. In both GLMs, regressors related to the tasks, distractors, and in the mathematical task, also cursor movement, are convolved with FSL's double-gamma function. First-level results (i.e., single run level) are combined using FEAT's fixed effects model to obtain participant-level results.

In addition to structural MRI and fMRI data, diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) data were collected in 2021 from the afore-mentioned 61 participants who performed both mathematical and semantic tasks. However, after data collection from them, it was realized that the experimental session needed to be shortened: The mathematical tasks (with short breaks between the runs) and structural MRI alone took together about 50 min, which nears the maximal time 12–14-year-olds can avoid moving in the MRI scanner, especially when this time is added to the initial scanning preparations taking 10–20 min. Since lying still during fMRI scanning is necessary for obtaining good-quality data, it was decided not to collect fMRI data during the semantic tasks or DTI data from further participants, as these data collections took together about 35 min. Nevertheless, it is possible to use the DTI data from these 61 participants to study strengths of neural tracts between cortical regions of interest (ROIs, see below) that would show functional and structural associations with ICT skills or use. To obtain DTI data, diffusion-weighted volumes (b value = 1000 s/mm²) were acquired using 64 diffusion sensitizing gradients with directions isotropically distributed on the surface of a unit sphere. The diffusion measurement was performed once, and a total of 10 non-diffusion-weighted images were acquired for reference.

3.2.3.1 Statistical analysis of fMRI and performance data

In the mathematical tasks, task performance is measured for each participant, as the average number of correct answers per block separately for each of the six combinations of task type (Solve, Create or Select) and auditory stimulation (dialogue plus babble distractor or its noise-vocoded equivalent). This measure depends on both speed and accuracy of participant's performance. In the semantic tasks, performance accuracy is measured as the number of correctly classified sentences.

Differences in performance and changes in brain activity caused by each task type or distractor, as well as associations of these effects with ICT use and skills, as well as other variables determined with the ySKILLS questionnaire are statistically tested with mixed analyses of variance. These analyses are performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 27 (IBM SPSS, Armonk, NY, USA). In addition to whole-head analysis of fMRI data we have a possibility to study effects of task and other variables in particular cortical ROIs showing task- and distractor-related activity changes in previous fMRI studies piloting the present mathematical and semantic experiments in young adults (Ylinen et al., 2022a; Moisala et al., 2015). In case significant effects of ICT skills or use are found in these ROIs, we can then study with the structural MRI data possible associations of ICT skills and use with cortical thickness in these areas to examine whether ICT use might have structural effects on the developing brain in adolescents (cf. Alho et al., 2022).

3.3 Associations of ICT skills and use with attention and working memory – a behavioural and structural MRI study

We originally planned to collect fMRI data in Belgium in a new sample of 12 to 14-year-olds with the same experimental paradigm as described in section 3.2.2. Due to COVID-19, it was not possible to collect these fMRI data and to execute the originally planned research project. Being limited to the collection of online data, we decided to additionally run an online study in sample of children in whom we had collected structural brain imaging data in a previous project (Bellon et al., 2020). The aim of that study was to investigate the associations between ICT skills and cognitive functions, that is, attention and working memory, that are the core focus of Task 4.5. This will allow us to understand the broader question of mechanism underlying individual differences in digital skills, particularly digital inequality (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2021). The primary reasons for investigating the associations between ICT use/skills and these cognitive functions is that (a) attention and working memory are critical determinants of performance in mathematical tasks (De Smedt, 2022; Spiegel et

al., 2021) (b) the neural correlates of these cognitive functions have been reliably identified in children and these are located in networks that encompass the (pre)frontal and (inferior) parietal cortices (e.g., Best & Miller, 2010). As a result, this study will help us to further understand the possible associations between ICT use/skills on mathematical performance in the fMRI study under section 3.2.2., where increases in brain activity in frontal and parietal cortices are to be expected during the execution of mathematical tasks (Peters & De Smedt, 2018; Vogel & De Smedt, 2021).

3.3.1 Participants

Data collection for this task originally started from the sample of children of Bellon et al. (2020), which consisted of 55 participants for which structural brain imaging data, i.e., high-resolution T1-weighted anatomical data of structural grey matter as well as Diffusion Tensor Imaging data of structural white matter were available. Regrettably, only 22 of the 55 children gave consent to participate in the study on ICT use/skills that is explained in more detail below. This number of $n = 22$ is too small to reliably calculate brain-behavior correlations. Although we could not collect additional brain imaging data, as described above, we decide to extend our sample to only collect data on ICT use/skills and cognitive measures, as these data could be collected online. The data could further serve to interpret the findings of the fMRI study described under section 3.2.2.

We additionally recruited 29 12–13-year-olds who all completed the cognitive tasks and filled the ySKILLS questionnaire on their ICT use and skills. A subsample of these children also completed the performance tests that measured their digital skills. All children and their legal guardians gave written informed consent to participate. The study was approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee of the KU Leuven, Belgium (G-2020-2901).

3.3.2 Measures

3.3.2.1 ICT skills and use

All participants completed the age-appropriate ICT skills and use questionnaire that was developed within the ySKILLS project (Helsper et al, 2020). This questionnaire tapped into the 4 dimensions of ICT skills and use, i.e. (1) technical and operational skills, (2) information, navigation and processing skills, (3) communication and interaction skills, (4) content creation and production skills, as well as childrens' confidence in ICT use, their amount of online activities, their sharing on social media and their knowledge about technology. These questionnaire data were collected online via Qualtrics.

A subsample of participants ($n = 19$) also performed a performance test to measure their ICT skills. The test consisted of a series of tasks in which the children had to search for information online, had to be critical towards online conversations and had to create online content. This test was executed online during a conversation with the researcher. Responses of the children were further coded via the coding scheme of Helsper et al. (2020).

3.3.2.1 Attention and working memory

Participants' attention and working memory were measured with classic widely used cognitive tasks, that is a flanker task and an n-back task respectively. Both tasks are known to tap into fronto-parietal networks (Best & Miller, 2010) and they are known to correlate with mathematical performance (e.g., Bellon et al., 2019). The tasks were the same as in Bellon et al. (2019). Both tasks were computerized and developed via Open Sesame (Mathôt et al., 2012). A link for online assessment was generated

via Jatos (Lange et al., 2015), which allowed the participants to complete the tasks independently online.

We used a classic arrow Flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974). In this speeded choice reaction time task, participants needed to respond to target stimuli (i.e., a left or right pointing arrow presented at the center of the screen) flanked by distractors (i.e., two arrows on each side of the target). These four distractor arrows either pointed in the same direction as the target, and thus indicated the same response (i.e., $\rightarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow$ or $\leftarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow$; congruent condition), or in the opposite direction of the target, and thus indicated the response that was incompatible with the target (i.e., $\rightarrow\rightarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow$ or $\leftarrow\leftarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow$; incongruent condition). Children had to indicate the direction of the middle arrow by pressing the corresponding key (i.e., left/right key) while suppressing the direction of the distractors. In total, 40 test items were administered, with 50% of the items being incongruent and the direction of the middle arrow being balanced. After fixation, stimuli appeared for 2500 ms, followed by a black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms. Before the task started, 12 trials were presented—used as a baseline condition for the analyses of this task—on which only one arrow was presented in the center of the screen (neutral condition). Children needed to indicate the direction of the arrow. RT and accuracy of the answers were registered by the computer. An inverse efficiency score (accuracy divided by RT) was used as a performance measure.

All participants completed a classic n-back task (Pelegriana et al., 2015). In this continuous recognition task, a sequence of items is shown. For each item, participants needed to indicate whether the presented stimulus was identical to the stimulus presented 2 trials back by answering yes or no. Items were colored images (e.g., rocket, sweater) presented one by one in the center of a white screen. In total, 40 items, divided into two blocks consisting of 20 trials each, were presented. In each block, 30% of the trials were target trials (i.e., correct answer = yes). The first 3 trials of each block were always nontarget items. After fixation, the stimulus appeared for 3000 ms, followed by a black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms. To familiarize the children with the task, one practice block (20 items) was presented. The performance measure was the accuracy of the answer.

3.3.3 Statistical analysis

Data will be analyzed via frequentist and Bayesian analyses. We will particularly examine the associations between the different dimensions of the ICT skills/use questionnaire and the cognitive tasks. We will also explore the associations between the ICT skills/use and performance tests.

The results of this study will help us to further understand the origins of individual differences in children's ICT skills and use (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2021). They also will deepen our understanding of the potential effects of ICT skills/use on math performance in the fMRI study (section 3.2) and they will help us to interpret the predicted brain activity related to distractor processing in fronto-parietal networks.

4 Summary

This report described the methods developed and used in the ySKILLS ESM and fMRI studies. The short-term influences of ICT skills and use on adolescents' wellbeing are investigated on a momentary and daily level with ESM, whereas the fMRI studies aim to examine their links to adolescents' cognitive skills and related brain activity. At the moment of writing this report D4.5 in December 2022 the data collection and (preliminary) analysis is still ongoing in both studies.

4.1 Summary of the ESM study

The methods used in the ESM study are designed to assess adolescents' ICT use and wellbeing on a momentary basis. This will likely yield more reliable information of the phenomena and their associations compared to more traditional self-report questionnaires. ESM is suited to capturing behaviour and experiences that are situational and context dependent. Moreover, the data are collected in real situations increasing the ecological validity, and the momentary nature of the assessment reduces retrospective bias. In addition, the data collection method supports the objectives of gaining information about within-person processes and revealing directionality of the effects under investigation. This kind of information is instrumental for creating and refining models predicting the complex effects of ICT use on adolescents' wellbeing.

There are also some limitations related to ESM. Although momentary, it is still a self-report method. Moreover, it is time-consuming for participants, technology-dependent and the assessments are likely to disrupt the processes that are studied. It is worth noting that, while momentary self-reports of adolescents' ICT use captured with ESM are more reliable compared to traditional self-reports, tracking log data from mobile app usage would yield even more accurate data. However, this was not possible with the available software. Nevertheless, ESM has the benefit of capturing the purposes and reasons for using certain apps and capturing variability across different situations and contexts.

As noted earlier, the onset of the ESM study was delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. While ESM has many benefits over traditional self-report questionnaires, it is an intensive data collection method that takes a considerable amount of time and effort from the participants. It also demands considerable amounts of time and resources from the researchers as well as the schools that take part and collaborate in the study. It seems that committing to such an intensive data collection was not feasible for schools suffering from the backwash of the pandemic. Moreover, recruiting participants in these circumstances proved to be challenging. These reasons led to the decision of delaying the first wave from the beginning of 2022 to the following autumn.

4.2 Summary of the fMRI study

The methods used in the ySKILLS fMRI studies are likely to give us reliable information on possible associations of ICT skills and use on cognitive functions and brain activity during attention-demanding tasks. First, both the mathematical and semantic tasks have been successfully applied in fMRI studies in young adults and they have revealed both brain activity related to specific tasks, brain activity related to control of attention, and modulations in brain activity due to attention-catching distractors (cf. Ylinen et al., 2022b; Moisala et al., 2015). Moreover, the paradigm used in the present semantic experiment was also used in a previous study in adolescents and young adults and revealed effects of ICT use (frequent multitasking) on distraction of task performance by task-irrelevant speech during reading and task-irrelevant written text during listening to speech, as well as on brain activity during distracted performance (Moisala et al., 2016).

If associations of ICT skills and use with fMRI participants performance accuracy or brain activity during the applied cognitive tasks were found, the question about causality in these associations would still remain open. Judging from previous studies (for a review, see Alho et al., 2022), it is likely that ICT use would affect, for example, the attention skills needed in the mathematical or semantic tasks at the presence of distracting task-irrelevant speech or written text, rather than participants' attention skills affecting the ways they use ICT. However, the only way to clarify this would be longitudinal research setting with two or more fMRI measurements, at sufficient intervals, in the same participants and experimental conditions. However, such repeated measurements are not possible with time and monetary resources allocated to ySKILLS project.

It should be noted that the ySKILLS fMRI data collection at the AMI Centre (Aalto University, Espoo, Finland) has been delayed by the COVID-19 pandemic. From August 2020 to June 2022, there was a mandatory 30-min disinfection break between successive fMRI measurements limiting substantially scanning time available for the numerous projects conducted at the AMI Centre, including the ySKILLS fMRI measurements. Fortunately, in addition to 80 adolescent fMRI participants studied with ySKILLS funding, we can add to the data analysis fMRI data from 105 adolescent participants of the Growing Mind project (funded by the Strategic Research Council of Finland) who filled the ySKILLS questionnaire and performed the same mathematical tasks as the ySKILLS participants. Moreover, we can compare possible effects of ICT skills and use on performance and brain activity in distracted and non-distracted mathematical tasks with such effects in distracted and non-distracted semantic tasks performed by 61 of the Growing Mind participants who also filled the ySKILLS questionnaire.

The originally planned parallel fMRI data collection in Belgium was not possible due to COVID-19 pandemic. Instead, in Belgium, online data were collected from a sample of 12–14-year-olds performing tasks that measure their attention and working memory skills. Fifty-one participants completed the ySKILLS questionnaire, and 19 of them also participated in the performance test that assessed their ICT skills. This set of data allows us to investigate the associations between ICT skills and use with attention and working memory. The latter are two cognitive functions that are closely linked to mathematical performance and of which the underlying brain networks have been reliably identified. This data will help us to further understand and interpreted the findings obtained in the fMRI study in Finland. More broadly, they help us to understand the origins of individual differences in ICT skills and use.

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Appendices

A. Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Thank you for your participation in our international ySKILLS project. Our goal is to better understand the use of internet and technologies by young people. To achieve this, we are asking you and other young participants European countries about your own experiences.

Here are some instructions about how to fill in the questionnaire.

Please read each question and take your time to answer. This is not a test and there are no right or wrong answers. This questionnaire is all about you, so it is important that you are as honest as possible. All your answers will be anonymised. If there is somebody else around you, ask them to not interrupt you and let you answer the questions alone.

You do not need to answer all of the questions. If you see a question that you cannot answer, or you are unhappy about answering it, please tick “I don’t know”, “Prefer not to say”, or move onto the next question.

Many of the questions are about the internet. Children and young people use the internet in lots of different ways and for lots of different reasons. When thinking about what you do on the internet, keep in mind all the technologies (e.g., laptop or mobile) and places (e.g., at home or somewhere else) where you may use it.

First, we will ask several questions about you.

How old are you?

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- Older than 17

What is your gender? Please, select which applies...

- Boy
- Girl
- Other

What language(s) do you speak at home most of the time? Select all, which applies.

(list of local languages in each country including the option “other”)

Now, we will ask you a few questions about how you used the INTERNET in the PAST MONTH.

About how long do you spend on the internet during a regular weekday (i.e., school day)?

- little or no time,
- about half an hour

- about 1 hour
- about 2 hours
- about 3 hours
- about 4 hours
- about 5 hours
- about 6 hours
- about 7 hours or more
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

About how long do you spend on the following social media platforms during a regular weekday (i.e., school day)?

	Little or no time	About half an hour	About 1 hour	About 2 hours	About 3 hours	About 4 hours	About 5 hours	About 6 hours	About 7 hours or more	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Facebook											
Instagram											
Twitter											
TikTok											
YouTube											
WhatsApp											
Facebook Messenger											
Telegram											
Snapchat											
Pinterest											
Reddit											
Discord											

In the past month, how often have you communicated on the internet with my friends or parents (e.g., via Messenger, email, WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, etc.)

- Never
- A few times
- At least every week
- Daily or almost daily
- Several times each day
- Almost all the time
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

Please indicate how true the following statements are of you when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones or computers. Reply thinking about how true this would be of you if you had to do it now, on your own.

If you do not understand what the question is asking, tick the box I don't understand what you mean by this.

	Not at all true of me	Not very true of me	Neither true nor untrue of me	Mostly true of me	Very true of me	I don't understand what you mean by this	I do not know	Prefer not to say
I know how to adjust privacy settings								
I know how to turn off the location settings on mobile devices								
I know how to protect a device (e.g. with a PIN, a screen pattern, a finger print, facial recognition)								
I know how to store photos, documents or other files in the cloud (e.g. Google Drive, iCloud)								
I know how to use private browsing (e.g. incognito mode)								
I know how to block unwanted pop-up messages or ads								
I know how to use programming language (e.g. XML, Python)								
I know how to choose the best keywords for online searches								
I know how to find a website I have visited before								
I know how to find information on a website no matter how it is designed								
I know how to use advanced search functions in search engines								
I know how to check if the information I find online is true								
I know how to figure out if a website can be trusted								
Depending on the situation, I know which medium or tool to use to communicate with someone (e.g., make a call, send a WhatsApp message, send an email)								

I know when I should mute myself or disable video in online interactions								
I know which images and information of me it is OK to share online								
I know when it is appropriate and when it is not appropriate to use emoticons (e.g. smileys, emojis), text speak (e.g. LOL, OMG) and capital letters								
I know how to report negative content relating to me or a group to which I belong								
I know how to recognise when someone is being bullied online								
I know how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g., photo, music, videos, GIFs)								
I know how to edit existing digital images, music and videos								
I know how to ensure that many people will see what I put online								
I know how to change the things I put online depending on how other people react to it								
I know how to distinguish sponsored and non-sponsored content online (e.g. in a video, in a social media post)								
I know how to reference and use content covered by copyright								

Now, we will ask you a few questions about whether and how you have followed the NEWS in the PAST MONTH.

People can follow the news in different ways. In a few sentences, can you describe how you keep up to date with the news?

(open question)

About how long do you spend following the news during a regular weekday (i.e., school day)? By news, we mean reporting on societal or political events.

- little or no time,
- about half an hour
- about 1 hour
- about 2 hours
- about 3 hours
- about 4 hours
- about 5 hours
- about 6 hours
- about 7 hours or more
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

How important is following the news to you?

- Not important at all
- Rather not important
- Neither not important nor important
- Rather important
- Very important
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

How often do you follow the news in the following ways?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost all the time	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Television							
Radio							
Printed newspapers							
Online news sites (add local examples here)							
Digital newspapers							
News apps (e.g. Google News, Apple News, add local example)							
Social media							

On which of the following social media platforms do you follow the news?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost all the time	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Facebook							
Instagram							
Twitter							
TikTok							
YouTube							
WhatsApp							
Facebook Messenger							
Telegram							
Snapchat							
Pinterest							
Reddit							

Discord							
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Please think about journalistic reporting in the news media. Do you believe that the news media (i.e., television news, newspapers, online news sites, ...) ...

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Are balanced							
Are objective							
Report the whole story							
Are accurate							
Are honest							
Are believable							

The next questions are about the news media. How would you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	Completely agree	I do not know	Prefer not to say
News companies choose stories based on what will attract the biggest audience									
Individuals can find news sources that reflect their own political values									
People pay more attention to news that fits with their beliefs than news that doesn't									
Two people might see the same news story and get different information from it									
News coverage of a political candidate will influence people's opinions									
Lighting is used to make certain people in the news look good or bad									

Below are some statements about ways in which people can evaluate the credibility of news. Reply thinking about how true this is of you.

	Not at all true of me	Not very true of me	Neither true nor untrue of me	Mostly true of me	Very true of me	I do not know	Prefer not to say
I make sure that I know all the information about the topic before I evaluate the credibility of the news article							
I evaluate the credibility of a news article in a thoughtful way							
I take the time to study all sides of the story before I evaluate the credibility of a news article							
Researching the facts is important to me for evaluating the credibility of a news article							
When I evaluate the credibility of a news article, I trust my gut feeling							
I trust my first impression about a news article when I evaluate its credibility							
I find my feeling more important than careful reflection when I evaluate the credibility of a news article							
When I evaluate the credibility of a news article, I only focus on certain aspects of the message instead of analyzing the entire message							
I do not spend much time when I evaluate the credibility of news							

How often do other people of your age share misinformation in the internet? With misinformation, we mean any information that is posted online that is not true (such as false news or gossip).

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Almost all the time
- I do not know

- Prefer not to say

How often do other people of your age use the following platforms for sharing misinformation? With misinformation, we mean any information that is posted online that is not true (such as false news or gossip).

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost all the time	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Facebook							
Instagram							
Twitter							
TikTok							
YouTube							
WhatsApp							
Facebook Messenger							
Telegram							
Snapchat							
Pinterest							
Reddit							
Discord							

On the internet, you may encounter to online contents that target individuals or communities on identified or supposed characteristics based on religion, origin, colour of skin or culture. This may cause people feeling they are treated unfairly because of their physical or personal characteristics, for example because of their physical appearance, their religion, where they come from or how they speak.

In the PAST 12 MONTHS, have you EVER seen hateful or degrading messages or comments online, against people or certain groups of people? (This could for example be Muslims, Migrants, Jews, Roma, etc.)?

- Never
- Once
- A few times
- At least every month
- At least every week
- Daily or almost daily
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

Considering such content on the internet, to what extent would you agree or disagree with the following statements? Such content...

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	Completely agree	I do not know	Prefer not to say
is just a part of using the internet									
does not have any long-lasting effects									
does not cause any real harm									

is not as serious as, for example, beating somebody up									
no one has ever died because of this									
there is nothing wrong with posting such content									

In the PAST 12 MONTHS, have you EVER received hateful or degrading messages or comments online, against you or your community? (This could for example be against Muslims, Migrants, Jews, etc.)?

- Never
- Once
- A few times
- At least every month
- At least every week
- Daily or almost daily
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

And in general, either online or offline, in the PAST 12 MONTHS, have you sometimes felt that you were treated badly in your daily life because of....

	Never	Once	A few times	At least every month	At least every week	Daily or almost daily	I do not know	Prefer not to say
your origin								
your skin colour								
your religion								
how you look like								

Which of the following best describes your financial situation and that of the people with whom you live?

- We live very well – We can purchase luxury items, like [ADD LOCAL EXAMPLES], and still have money left over
- We live well – We have enough money to afford most things without having to save for them
- We get by ok – We have enough for everyday things, but we have to save for more serious purchases and expenses
- We live modestly – We have to manage our money carefully and limit our daily spending
- We struggle to get by – We sometimes do not have enough money to afford basic needs, such as food and clothes
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

Now, we will ask several things about you.

In general, how would you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Often	Always	I do not know	Prefer not to say
When a friend is scared, I feel afraid							
When my friend is sad, I become sad too							
When a friend is angry, I feel angry too							
When people around me are nervous, I become nervous too							

In general, how true are these things of you?

	Not true	A bit true	Fairly true	Very true	I do not know	Prefer not to say
It is easy for me to stick to my aims and achieve my goals						
I can solve most problems if I try hard						
If I am in trouble I can usually think of something to do						
I can generally work out how to handle new situations						

In general, considering people around you, how easy or difficult are following things for you?

	Very difficult	Difficult	Not difficult, not easy	Easy	Very easy	I do not know	Prefer not to say
Listen carefully to someone who told you about a problem he or she is experiencing							
Comfort someone who is feeling down							
Help others cope with an unpleasant experience							
Help someone when he or she asked you							
Help someone to feel at ease							

In general, how much do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree	I do not know	Prefer not to say
I don't like to have to do a lot of thinking							
I try to avoid situations that require							

thinking in depth about something							
I prefer to do something that challenges my thinking abilities rather than something that requires little thought							
I prefer complex to simple problems							
Thinking hard and for a long time about something gives me little satisfaction							

This is the end of the questionnaire. Thank you for your participation.

B. Appendix 2: ESM study: Daily questionnaire

Instruction	What were you doing when you got the survey?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I was in class 2. I was in school, but not in class 3. I had free time/not in school 4. Something else, what?

Instruction	Were you using any technology or device?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1. Yes
Instruction	What were you doing specifically? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. communicating with others 2. browsing social media 3. browsing websites (e.g. news, information) 4. watching series/movie/program (e.g. netflix) 5. playing 6. creating pictures/videos/blog texts 7. listening to music 8. something else, what?

Condition	2. browsing social media
Instruction	What social media platform were you using? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. Something else, what?

Condition	3. browsing websites (e.g. news, information)
Instruction	What kind of content were you browsing through? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what?

Condition	6. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself
Instruction	Did you share your photos/videos/blogtexts
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1 yes
Instruction	On which social media platform(s)? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. some other, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	How well do the following words describe your feelings now? At the moment I feel:
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. enthusiastic 2. distressed 3. bored 4. tired 5. anxious 6. relaxed 7. frustrated 8. curious 9. lonely 10. restless
Response options	1 not at all – 7 very much

C. Appendix 3: ESM study: Morning questionnaire

Instruction	What did you do during the last 30 minutes before going to sleep? You can choose multiple options
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I read a book 2. I spent some time with my family 3. I messaged/communicated with others 4. I did schoolwork 5. I browsed social media 6. I browsed websites (e.g., news, information) 7. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself 8. I watched a series/movie/program (e.g., Netflix) 9. I listened to music 10. something else, what? 11. I don't remember

Condition	5. I browsed social media
Instruction	What social media did you browse? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TikTok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. YouTube 5. Facebook 6. news website or app 7. some other, what? 8. I don't remember

Condition	6. I browsed websites (e.g., news, information)
Instruction	What types of websites did you browse? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Condition	7. I created photos/videos/blogtexts myself
Instruction	Did you share your photos/videos/blogtexts
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	On which social media platform(s)? You can pick multiple options:
Response options	1. Tiktok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. Youtube 5. Facebook 6. some other, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	At what time did you go to sleep? (That is, turned off the lights and devices and went to bed, e.g. 22.15)
Response options	Time

Instruction	Did you use your phone in bed right before you started to sleep?
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	Did you fall asleep easily?
Response options	1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	How well did you sleep last night?
Response options	1. well 2. quite well 3. moderately 4. quite badly 5. badly

Instruction	At what time did you wake up in the morning?
Response options	Time

Instruction	Did you use your phone in bed immediately as you woke up this morning?
--------------------	--

Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Yes2. No
-------------------------	--

D. **Appendix 4: ESM study: Evening questionnaire**

Instruction	Did you share a news item online today?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. Yes
Instruction	Did you read the news item that you shared?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Condition	1. What was the news item about?
Instruction	Did you read the news item that you shared?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No

Instruction	Have you seen a news item today that made you doubt whether it was real or fake?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	Where did you see it?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1 TikTok 2. Instagram 3. Snapchat 4. YouTube 5. Facebook 6. news website or app 7. television 8. radio 9. somewhere else, where? 10. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	What was the fake-news about?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. politics (e.g. war) 2. economics 3. health (e.g. covid19) 4. entertainment, media, art and culture 5. sports 6. something else, what? 7. I don't remember

Instruction	Did you read online comments today?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No 3. I don't remember

Condition	1. yes
Instruction	What types of comments did you encounter? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. funny 2. offensive 3. informative 4. other 5. I don't remember/I don't know

Condition	2. offensive
Instruction	Where did you encounter offensive comments? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 TikTok 2 Instagram 3 Snapchat 4 YouTube 5 Facebook 6 news website or app 7 somewhere else, where? 8 I don't remember

Condition	2. offensive
Instruction	At whom were the offensive comments directed at? You can choose multiple options:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 me personally 2 some other person 3 the group I belong to or identify with (e.g., gender, ethnicity) 4 a group someone else is part of/identifies with (e.g., gender, ethnicity) 5 I don't know/I'm not sure

Instruction	Using digital devices today (e.g. mobile phone), I felt that I...:
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. learned something new? 2. made a difference? 3. got to express myself? 4. was part of a group/collective?
Response options	1 not at all – 5 very much

Instruction	Outside school / in your free time: How much face-to-face -time did you spend with your friends today?
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all 2. Less than an hour 3. 1-2 hours 4. more than 2 hours

Instruction	Now think about your social media use today...: During the day, ...
Items	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ...I felt bad when I could not use social media? 2. ...I had arguments with others because of my social media use? 3. ...I lied to my parents or friends about the amount of time I spend on social media?
Response options	1 not at all – 5 very much

Instruction	Please go to your screentime view on your phone settings and indicate here what were and how much time you spent today on the three most used apps:
Response options	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Most used app 2. Second most used app 3. Third most used app
	Open and Hours and minutes

E. Appendix 5: ESM study: Participant informed consent forms

Finland

Hei lukiolainen

Tulit keväällä 2021 mukaan kansainväliseen nuorten digitaalisen teknologian käyttöä ja hyvinvointia seuraavaan ySKILLS -pitkittäistutkimukseen. Osa tästä tutkimuksesta toteutetaan tänä ja ensi vuonna (2022 ja 2023) nuorten omilla älypuhelimilla ja aktiivisuusrannekeilla. Pyydämme sinua osallistumaan tähän osioon.

Tutkimus pähkinänkuoressa

- Lataat puhelimesi tutkimussovelluksen, joka lähettää useita lyhyitä kysymyssarjoja päivittäin, kahden viikon aikana.
- Aktiivisuusseurantaan osallistuvat käyttävät samanaikaisesti aktiivisuusranneketta vuorokauden ympäri.
- Tutkimuksen jälkeen sovellus poistetaan puhelimesta ja ranneke palautetaan tutkijaryhmälle.

Laajemmin, mitä ja keitä tutkitaan?

ySKILLS on EU:n rahoittama kansainvälinen kolmevuotinen tutkimushanke (2020-2023), jonka tarkoituksena on seurata nuorten kasvua ja kehitystä peruskoulun ja toisen asteen opintojen aikana. Tutkimuksessa kerätään oppilailta kyselylomakkeiden avulla tietoa heidän digiteknologian käytöstä, yleisestä hyvinvoinnista, taustasta sekä kouluarvosanoista.

Älypuhelinsoviossa tutkimme, miten digitaalisen teknologian päivittäinen käyttö heijastuu nuoren tunteisiin, ajatteluun ja hyvinvointiin. Älypuhelinsoviossa lataat m-Path -tutkimussovelluksen puhelimesi (App store/Google play). Sovellus lähettää lyhyitä kysymyssarjoja (kesto n. 1 minuutti) kuudesti päivässä, kahden viikon ajan. Samanaikaisesti osa nuorista pitää aktiivisuusrannekeita (Axivity AX3) aktiivisuuden, vuorokausirytmien ja unen keston arvioimiseksi. Ranneketta tulee pitää koko tutkimusjakson ajan (myös nukkuessa). Ranneketta voi pitää suihkun aikana, mutta halutessaan laitteen saa ottaa pois suihkuun mentäessä. Ranneke tulee ottaa pois myös liikuntaa harrastettaessa, jos liikunta voi vaurioittaa ranneketta tai sen pitäminen on muulla tavoin ongelmallista urheilulajin/käyttäjän kannalta (esim. paini, nyrkkeily, uinti).

Tutkimuksen jälkeen m-Path-sovellus poistetaan puhelimesta ja ranneke palautetaan tutkijaryhmälle. Asiasta on sovittu koulujen ja opettajien kanssa, jotta vastaamisesta aiheutuisi mahdollisimman vähän häiriötä oppilaalle ja muille.

Keräämämme aineisto tuottaa uutta tietoa nuorten digitaalisen teknologian käytön, hyvinvoinnin, tunteiden, ajatusten ja aktiivisuuden yhteyksistä. Tiedon avulla voit oppia tukemaan positiivista kehitystäsi ja sekä vanhemmat että opettajat voivat tukea nuoren positiivista kehitystä. Kaikkia kerättyjä tietoja tutkitaan täysin yleisellä tasolla, pseudonymisoidulla aineistolla, eikä yksittäistä henkilöä voida tunnistaa vastauksista. Tutkimuksen etenemisestä tiedotetaan lukuvuosittain.

Tutkimuksen vapaaehtoisuus, tutkimuksen keskeyttäminen ja suostumuksen peruuttaminen

- Oppilaalla on oikeus milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana *keskeyttää* tutkimukseen osallistuminen. Syyt keskeytykselle ei tarvitse ilmoittaa. Tutkimuksesta kieltäytymisellä tai sen keskeyttämisellä ei ole jälkiseurauksia eikä se vaikuta oppilaan kohteluun millään tavalla nyt tai tulevaisuudessa. Keskeytyksen jälkeen oppilaasta ei enää kerätä uutta tietoa, mutta keskeyttämiseen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja käytetään osana tutkimusaineistoa.
- Oppilaan on myös mahdollista *peruuttaa* suostumus tutkimukseen, jolloin kaikki henkilötiedot ja tutkimuksessa kerätty osallistujaa koskeva aineisto poistetaan eikä sitä käytetä tutkimuksen osana. Tutkimuksen keskeyttämisestä tai suostumuksen peruuttamisesta ilmoitetaan tässä kirjeessä yhteyshenkilöksi kirjatulle henkilölle. Kerätty tutkimusaineisto kuitenkin anonymisoidaan syksyllä 2023, minkä jälkeen tietoja ei voida enää poistaa.

Luottamuksellisuus, tietojen käsittely, säilytys ja arkistointi

Tutkimushankkeen tutkijat noudattavat tiukkoja turvallisuusohjeita. Kaikki oppilaiden antamat tiedot ovat ehdottoman luottamuksellisia.

- Nimi ei tule olemaan tulosten tallentamisen jälkeen näkyvissä missään, henkilöllisyys ei käy ilmi tutkimuksen tuloksista eivätkä yksittäisten vastaajien tiedot missään vaiheessa tule kenenkään Helsingin yliopiston ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän ulkopuolisen tietoon.
- Oppilaan suostumuksella älypuhelimella ja aktiivisuusrannekeella kerättäviä tietoja yhdistetään toisiinsa sekä muuhun ySKILLS-tutkimuksessa hänestä kerättäviin ja jo kerättyihin tietoihin. Näitä tietoja ovat tutkimuksen pitkäaikaiskyselyaineisto (kevät 2021, 2022 ja 2023) ja oppilaiden arvosanat.
- Kaikkia tutkimusaineistoja käsitellään ja säilytetään tietoturvasuosittain EU:n yleisen tietosuojalain ja -asetuksen sekä tietosuojalain edellyttämällä tavalla. Tutkimuksen aineistoa ja osanottajien uudelleen tavoittamiseksi tarvittavaa nimi- ja yhteystietolistaa säilytetään erillään, jolloin kenenkään yksittäisen osallistujan henkilöllisyys ei paljastu.
- Tutkimusaineistoon ja vastauksiin pääsevät käsiksi vain Helsingin yliopiston ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän jäsenet. Tutkimusryhmän ulkopuolisten tutkijoiden on myös mahdollista päästä käyttämään tutkimusaineistoa mutta vain läheisessä yhteistyössä ySKILLS-tutkimusryhmän kanssa. Voit kysyä lisätietoja tutkimuksesta tutkijoilta.

Osallistumisesi on tutkimuksen onnistumisen kannalta erittäin tärkeää!

Suomessa tutkimuksesta vastaa akatemiaprofessori Katariina Salmela-Aro Helsingin yliopiston kasvatustieteellisestä tiedekunnasta.

Yhteyshenkilöt ja lisätietoja:

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Englanninkieliset verkkosivut: <https://yskills.eu/>

Päiväys: 17.8.2022

Link: <https://www.oppimisanalytiikka.fi/hankeinfot/yskills/tutkimustiedote/>

Olen lukenut suostumustiedotteen (linkki yllä) ja vahvistan osallistumiseni tähän tutkimukseen sekä hyväksyn antamani tietojen käyttämisen tutkimustarkoitukseen.

1. Kyllä

2. Ei

NEXT QUESTION

ySkills_Consent

Sallin kerättävän aineiston yhdistämisen muuhun ySKILLS-tutkimuksessa kerättyyn aineistoon.

1. Kyllä

2. Ei

TOESTEMMINGSFORMULIER JONGEREN

Beste jongere,

- Gedurende twee weken krijg je zes keer per dag een paar korte vragen. Op een paar minuten zijn de vragen ingevuld.
 - Voor deze studie gebuiken we een smartphone app, m-Path, ontwikkeld aan de KU Leuven. Deze app is conform de huidige privacy wetgeving (GDPR). Je installeert de app tijdelijk op je eigen smartphone. De app registreert enkel de antwoorden op de vragen, er worden geen andere (achtergrond)data geregistreerd.
 - Deelname aan het onderzoek is volledig anoniem.
 - Deelname is vrijwillig en je kan op elk moment je deelname stopzetten zonder een reden te geven, en zonder nadelige gevolgen.
 - Deze ESM studie (Experience Sampling Method, of dagboekstudie) zal op drie verschillende momenten plaatsvinden, met telkens ongeveer zes maanden tussen: mei 2022, oktober 2022 en mei 2023. Het onderzoek loopt parallel ook in Finland.
 - Dit langetermijnonderzoek geeft ons unieke inzichten in de mentale gezondheid en dagelijkse activiteiten van jongeren. Op die manier kunnen we betere ondersteuning garanderen voor een positieve ontwikkeling van jongeren.
 - Dit onderzoeksproject wordt gefinancierd door de Europese Commissie en heeft ethische goedkeuring gekregen van de LSE Research Ethics Committee (Ref 23512/30.07.2021).
1. Ik heb de informatie over het ySKILLS ESM onderzoek gelezen en **IK WIL DEELNEMEN** aan het ESM onderzoek
 2. **IK WIL NIET DEELNEMEN** aan het ySKILLS ESM onderzoek

Naam: _____

Voornaam: _____

Plaats en datum: _____

TOESTEMMINGSFORMULIER OUDERS EN VOOGDEN

Beste ouder of voogd,

- Gedurende twee weken krijgen jongeren zes keer per dag een paar korte vragen. Op een paar minuten zijn de vragen ingevuld.
- Voor deze studie gebruiken we een smartphone app, m-Path, ontwikkeld aan de KU Leuven. Deze app is conform de huidige privacy wetgeving (GDPR). De jongere installeert de app tijdelijk op zijn of haar eigen smartphone. De app registreert enkel de antwoorden op de vragen, er worden geen andere (achtergrond)data geregistreerd.
- Deelname aan het onderzoek is volledig anoniem.
- Deelname is vrijwillig en de jongere kan op elk moment zijn of haar deelname stopzetten zonder een reden te geven, en zonder nadelige gevolgen.
- Deze ESM studie (Experience Sampling Method, of dagboekstudie) zal op drie verschillende momenten plaatsvinden, met telkens ongeveer zes maanden tussen: mei 2022, oktober 2022 en mei 2023. Het onderzoek loopt parallel ook in Finland.
- Dit langetermijnonderzoek geeft ons unieke inzichten in de mentale gezondheid en dagelijkse activiteiten van jongeren. Op die manier kunnen we betere ondersteuning garanderen voor een positieve ontwikkeling van jongeren.
- Dit onderzoeksproject wordt gefinancierd door de Europese Commissie en heeft ethische goedkeuring gekregen van de LSE Research Ethics Committee (Ref 23512/30.07.2021).

Wij verzoeken u vriendelijk de volgende informatie zorgvuldig te lezen. **Door dit document te ondertekenen bevestigt u dat u het volgende begrijpt en ermee akkoord gaat:**

- Ik heb de informatiebrief voor dit onderzoek gelezen en de inhoud ervan volledig begrepen.
- Ik geef mijn toestemming voor de deelname van mijn kind aan dit onderzoeksproject.
- Ik begrijp dat deelname aan dit project vrijwillig is en dat het mogelijk is om op elk moment van deelname af te zien.
- Ik sta toe dat de gegevens van mijn kind worden bewaard en gebruikt in toekomstig onderzoek binnen het ySKILLS-project.
- Ik begrijp dat de anonieme gegevens van dit onderzoek kunnen worden gepubliceerd in academische publicaties, gedeeld in een open archief.

F. Appendix 6: fMRI study: Participant and guardian informed consent form

Please, note that in these consent forms, the research project is titled Developing Mind and Brain, as this is the title in the ethical approval by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital District of Helsinki and Uusimaa for a series of fMRI studies in adolescents, including the ySKILLS fMRI study, conducted at the Advanced Magnetic Imaging Center, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland, by Attention and Memory Networks Research Group directed by Prof. Kimmo Alho at the Department of Psychology and Logopedics, Faculty of Medicine, University of Helsinki.

Tutkimusnumero _____

Suostumus tutkimukseen osallistumisesta 11–14-vuotiaat: Developing Mind and Brain -aivotutkimus

Minua on pyydetty mukaan tutkimukseen, johon huoltajani on jo antanut minulle luvan osallistua. Minua on pyydetty mukaan tutkimukseen, koska olen terve koulua käyvä lapsi. Olen saanut tietoa tutkimuksesta tutkijoilta ja tutkittavan tiedotteesta ja ymmärrän, että tutkimuksessa selvitetään kuinka eri ikäisten lasten ja nuorten aivot toimivat erilaisten tehtävien aikana. Ymmärrän, että tutkimukseen osallistuminen on täysin vapaaehtoista ja tiedän, että voin halutessani perua suostumukseni tai keskeyttää tutkimuksen missä tahansa tutkimuksen vaiheessa. Tutkimuksen aikana käyn kerran tutkimuslaboratoriossa. Tutkijat saattavat pyytää minua myöhemmin mukaan samanlaiseen tutkimukseen, mutta minun ei tarvitse vielä päättää, haluanko osallistua siihen. Minulle on kerrottu, että vain minä ja tutkimuksen tutkijat saavat nähdä minulta kerättyjä tutkimustietoja. Tutkimuksesta kieltäytyminen tai tutkimukseen osallistumisen keskeyttäminen tai suostumuksen peruminen ei vaikuta mitenkään muuhun mahdollisesti saamaani hoitoon.

Osallistun Developing Mind and Brain –tutkimukseen..... KYLLÄ EI

Paikka ja pvm

Tutkittavan allekirjoitus ja nimenselvennys

Henkilötunnus

Suostumuksen vastaanottajan allekirjoitus ja nimenselvennys

Tästä lomakkeesta on kaksi kappaletta, yksi tutkittavalle ja yksi tutkijalle.

Tutkimusnumero _____

Huoltajan suostumus alaikäisen lapsen osallistumisesta Developing Mind and Brain -tutkimukseen

Olen saanut selvityksen Helsingin yliopiston psykologian ja logopedian osaston järjestämästä tutkimuksesta. Ymmärrän, että minulta tiedustellaan lupaa lapseni/huollettavani osallistumiseen ko. tutkimukseen. Ymmärrän, että tutkimukseen osallistuminen on täysin vapaaehtoista ja että tutkimuksesta voi kieltäytyä myös tämän suostumuksen jälkeen syytä ilmoittamatta ilman että siitä koituu mitään seuraamuksia tutkittavalle. Olen tietoinen siitä, että jos toinen alaikäisen huoltajista on tutkimusta vastaan, ei lapseni/huollettavani voi osallistua siihen. Olen tietoinen, että tutkimuksessa kerättävää tietoa käytetään nimettömästi tieteellisten julkaisujen materiaalina siten, ettei tutkittavaa voi tunnistaa ja tutkimustiedot säilytetään erillään henkilötiedoista. Peruuttaessani suostumukseni tai keskeyttäessäni tutkimuksen siihen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja ja näytteitä käytetään osana tutkimusaineistoa, koska se on välttämätöntä tutkimustulosten varmistamiseksi. Alaikäisen tutkittavan tietoja ei luovuteta ilman huoltajan lupaa tutkijaryhmän ulkopuolelle. Tutkimuksesta kieltäytyminen tai tutkimukseen osallistumisen keskeyttäminen tai suostumuksen peruminen ei vaikuta mitenkään muuhun mahdollisesti lapseni saamaan hoitoon.

Lapseni/huollettavani saa osallistua Developing Mind and Brain -
tutkimukseen..... KYLLÄ EI

Lapsen/huollettavan nimi

Lapsen henkilötunnus

Osoite

Huoltajan 1 puhelinnumero (ja sähköpostiosoite)

Paikka ja päivämäärä

Huoltajan 1 allekirjoitus ja nimenselvitys

Huoltajan 2 puhelinnumero (ja sähköpostiosoite)

Paikka ja päivämäärä

Huoltajan 2 allekirjoitus ja nimenselvitys

Suostumuksen vastaanottajan allekirjoitus ja nimenselvitys

